

Essential pharmacology of bupropion: a structured compilation

Integration of mechanisms, metabolism, and clinical profile

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Abstract This work provides a basic and compiled overview of the pharmacology of bupropion, integrating in a structured manner the most relevant aspects of its mechanisms of action, metabolism, interactions, and clinical safety profile. Its main therapeutic uses as an antidepressant and smoking cessation agent are reviewed, as well as its application in other contexts such as attention deficit hyperactivity disorder. Pharmacokinetic and metabolic considerations are discussed, emphasizing the role of active metabolites in the drug's therapeutic activity. The document aims to offer an accessible, evidence-based synthesis, serving as a starting point for students, researchers, and healthcare professionals seeking a general understanding of the pharmacological foundations of this compound.

Keywords: Pharmacology; bupropion; Mechanism of action; metabolism; antidepressant

Resumen El presente trabajo ofrece una visión básica y compilada de la farmacología del bupropión, integrando de forma estructurada los aspectos más relevantes sobre sus mecanismos de acción, metabolismo, interacciones y perfil de seguridad clínica. Se revisan sus principales usos terapéuticos como antidepresivo y agente para la cesación tabáquica, así como su aplicación en otros contextos como el trastorno por déficit de atención e hiperactividad. Además, se abordan consideraciones farmacocinéticas y metabólicas, destacando el papel de sus metabolitos activos en la actividad terapéutica del fármaco. El documento busca proporcionar una síntesis accesible y fundamentada, útil como punto de partida para estudiantes, investigadores y profesionales interesados en comprender de manera general los fundamentos farmacológicos de este compuesto.

Palabras claves: Farmacología; bupropión; mecanismo de acción; metabolismo; antidepresivo

Introduction: Bupropion is an aminoketone-structured drug classified as an atypical antidepressant because its mechanism of action differs from other antidepressants such as tricyclics or serotonin reuptake inhibitors, and its efficacy is comparable to that of other agents [1](#), [2](#). Su uso se remite al tratamiento del trastorno depresivo mayor [3](#) y la terapia para dejar de fumar [4](#).

In general, bupropion is considered to have no effect on serotonergic pathways, as it shows little to no affinity for either pre- or postsynaptic serotonin receptors [1](#), [5](#). However, some studies have reported the occurrence of serotonin syndrome in cases of bupropion overdose, although this is mainly attributed to the effects of its metabolites, which are discussed later [6](#).

The purpose of this work is to provide a basic and compiled overview of the pharmacology of bupropion, concisely integrating its main mechanisms of action, metabolism, interactions, and safety profile. The information available on this drug is often scattered across different sources and perspectives; therefore, this work aims to present a clear and structured synthesis that facilitates a general understanding and serves as a starting point for future reviews focused on specific aspects, such as its potential immunomodulatory effects.

Mechanisms of action

Mechanism as an antidepressant

The antidepressant mechanism of bupropion is based on the inhibition of active norepinephrine (NA) and dopamine (DA) transporters at the presynaptic level, which prevents their reuptake and prolongs

their availability in the synaptic cleft [1](#), [5](#). In addition, bupropion has been described as participating in the redistribution of the vesicular monoamine transporter type 2 (VMAT2), which is responsible for regulating cytoplasmic dopamine concentrations in neuronal terminals by storing it within synaptic vesicles [7](#). Taken together, these mechanisms lead to increased concentrations of NA and DA in the synaptic cleft, enhancing monoaminergic transmission and explaining its clinical efficacy, which represents its primary therapeutic use. ([Figure 1](#)).

Mechanism in smoking cessation

On the other hand, the action of bupropion in smoking cessation therapy is based on the increase of neurotransmitter levels, which helps alleviate withdrawal symptoms and reduce the craving for nicotine [2](#), [8](#). Additionally, bupropion exerts a non-competitive antagonistic effect on nicotinic receptors, which contributes to reducing the effects of nicotine [8](#), [9](#), [10](#).

In animal models, bupropion has been shown to modulate nicotine-influenced brain reward circuits by enhancing baseline reward function, blocking the acute reinforcing effects of nicotine, and reversing the affective and somatic aspects of withdrawal [11](#). Although most of this evidence comes from preclinical studies, research in humans has reported parallel observations, such as a transient increase in smoking behavior following bupropion pretreatment in individuals who were not attempting to quit, suggesting a dose-dependent interaction between dopaminergic mechanisms and nicotine reinforcement processes [5](#), [11](#), [12](#).

Other clinical applications and their pharmacological foundations

Although the primary effects of bupropion are related to the treatment of depressive disorders and smoking cessation, it has also been included among the therapeutic options for managing attention-deficit/hyperactivity disorder (ADHD) in adults, with some evidence supporting symptom reduction and clinical improvement [12](#). This effect is due to the fact that the pathophysiology of ADHD is associated with a dysfunction of the dopaminergic and noradrenergic networks that connect the prefrontal cortex, the striatum (particularly the caudate nucleus), and the cerebellum. These areas regulate attention, impulse control, and motivation, and their activity depends on the balance between DA and NA [13](#). Therefore, the interaction with these amine pathways supports its therapeutic use [1, 14, 15](#).

Other important mechanisms or effects of bupropion include its use in combination with naltrexone for the treatment of excessive alcohol consumption [16](#), modest weight loss in cases of obesity [17](#), and generalized social phobia [18](#).

Pharmacokinetic and metabolic considerations

Absorption, distribution and elimination

Bupropion formulations are completely absorbed in the gastrointestinal tract [19](#). Bupropion exhibits a high volume of distribution and minimal renal excretion in unchanged form [19, 20, 21](#). Due to hepatic first-pass metabolism, its absolute bioavailability is quantitatively low [19, 21](#);

However, some authors consider this clinically insignificant, as the activity of its metabolites largely compensates for the low bioavailability [21](#).

The half-life of bupropion varies between 8 and 39 hours depending on the formulation and individual metabolism, with an approximate average of 21 ± 9 hours for a dosage of 150 mg administered twice daily [19, 21](#).

Metabolism, active metabolites, and their effect

Bupropion is metabolized in the liver by cytochrome P450 2B6 enzyme (CYP2B6), where hydroxybupropion is produced as a metabolite with up to 50% of the activity of the original drug [19, 21, 22](#). Bupropion is metabolized by the hepatic carbonyl reductase (CR) enzyme as well, and this process produces the active metabolites threohydrobupropion and erythrohydrobupropion, which have a potency ranging from 20% to 50% [20, 22](#).

The active metabolites of bupropion, primarily hydroxybupropion, threohydrobupropion, and erythrohydrobupropion, contribute a significant portion of its overall pharmacological effect. Hydroxybupropion reaches plasma concentrations 10 to 20 times higher than those of the parent drug [21](#). These substances have longer half-lives than unchanged bupropion: approximately 20 ± 5 hours for hydroxybupropion, and 33 ± 10 and 37 ± 13 hours for erythrohydrobupropion and threohydrobupropion, respectively. Altogether, bupropion and its metabolites require 7 to 10 days to reach steady state, exhibiting linear pharmacokinetics at doses

of 300 to 450 mg/day, with renal excretion of the unchanged drug close to 0.5% [19](#), [21](#). Given that the metabolites demonstrate substantial and sustained pharmacological activity, the low oral bioavailability of bupropion is of limited clinical significance. This is because the overall therapeutic effect relies largely on the generation and prolonged presence of these active compounds rather than on the parent drug alone [19](#), [21](#).

Pharmacogenetic variability

A relevant aspect of the pharmacokinetic variability of bupropion is the genetic influence on its metabolism. In particular, the CYP2B6*6 allele and the poor or intermediate metabolizer phenotypes determined by the CYP2B6 genotype are associated with lower plasma concentrations of hydroxybupropion and of the total sum of the parent drug and its active metabolites [22](#).

Relevant interactions

Pharmacodynamic interactions

The pharmacodynamic interactions of bupropion are mainly related to its effects on the central nervous system (CNS) and the risk of neurological or psychiatric events. Concomitant use with levodopa or amantadine may increase the risk of CNS toxicity and dopaminergic effects such as psychosis, hallucinations, tremors, or agitation [23](#). Likewise, concomitant administration with antipsychotics, tricyclic antidepressants, theophylline, or systemic

corticosteroids significantly increases the risk of seizures [23](#).

In addition, the combination with selective serotonin reuptake inhibitors (such as paroxetine, fluoxetine, or sertraline) or with antipsychotics (haloperidol, risperidone, thioridazine) is associated with an increased risk of neuropsychiatric adverse effects [23](#).

Pharmacokinetic interactions

The pharmacokinetic interactions of bupropion are primarily associated with the induction or inhibition of cytochrome P450 enzymes, particularly CYP2B6 and CYP2D6, which determine its plasma concentrations and those of its active metabolites [23](#).

Drugs such as ritonavir, lopinavir, efavirenz, carbamazepine, phenytoin, and phenobarbital act as inducers of CYP2B6, reducing plasma concentrations of bupropion and potentially decreasing its therapeutic efficacy. In contrast, ticlopidine and clopidogrel are CYP2B6 inhibitors, leading to increased plasma levels of bupropion and decreased concentrations of hydroxybupropion, its main active metabolite [23](#).

Bupropion also acts as an inhibitor of the CYP2D6 isoenzyme, an enzyme involved in the metabolic activation of several drugs. This inhibition may interfere with the conversion of tamoxifen to its active metabolites, thereby reducing its therapeutic effectiveness. Finally, bupropion has been reported to decrease plasma concentrations of digoxin, which may compromise its therapeutic effect; therefore, close monitoring and dose adjustments may be necessary during concomitant use [23](#).

Adverse effects of Bupropion

Common effects

Bupropion is generally considered a well-tolerated drug; however, its effects on the dopaminergic and noradrenergic systems can predict certain adverse reactions. Accordingly, the most common effects include dry mouth, headache, nausea, constipation, insomnia, agitation, and weight loss [1](#), [2](#), [3](#), [5](#), [21](#), [23](#).

Serious adverse effects

The risk of seizures represents a clinically significant adverse event, particularly at high doses or in patients with predisposing factors such as a history of epilepsy, eating disorders, or the use of alcohol and central nervous system depressants [1](#), [3](#), [5](#), [24](#). In overdose scenarios, tonic-clonic seizures, agitation, hallucinations, hypertension, and tachycardia have been reported, although fatal outcomes are uncommon [5](#). Additionally, mild serotonergic toxicity has been observed in a significant proportion of patients following isolated bupropion overdose, highlighting the need for close clinical monitoring for signs of increased serotonergic activity or seizures [6](#), [25](#).

Comparative profile

Sustained-release (SR) and extended-release (XL) formulations have been shown to improve tolerability by reducing plasma peaks and, consequently, the incidence of stimulant effects such as agitation or insomnia [3](#), [21](#). Nevertheless, hypertension may occasionally occur, particularly in the

context of combined treatment with nicotine patches [2](#), [3](#). Allergic and delayed hypersensitivity reactions have also been reported, including urticaria, angioedema, and fever with arthralgias [5](#).

Compared with other antidepressants, bupropion has a lower incidence of sexual dysfunction, somnolence, and anticholinergic effects, which distinguishes it favorably from selective serotonin reuptake inhibitors and tricyclic antidepressants [2](#), [3](#), [21](#). In general, its side effects usually appear at the beginning of treatment and tend to diminish with continued use, maintaining a favorable safety profile during prolonged therapy [3](#), [5](#), [21](#).

Final considerations

Bupropion is an atypical antidepressant with a distinctive pharmacological profile, based on the inhibition of dopamine and norepinephrine reuptake. Its efficacy in depression, smoking cessation, and ADHD reflects the versatility of its action. The active metabolites, particularly hydroxybupropion, contribute significantly to its clinical effect and explain the limited relevance of its oral bioavailability. Although generally well tolerated, the risk of seizures at high doses or in predisposed patients requires caution.

This review emphasizes the importance of a thorough understanding of bupropion's pharmacology to optimize its therapeutic use. Its clinical versatility and distinctive adverse effect profile make it a valuable treatment option. Future research on its immunomodulatory effects, as will be explored in subsequent studies, could reveal new dimensions of its pharmacological activity.

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Compilation of basic information about bupropion

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Images:

Figure 1: Mechanism of action of bupropion.

A, Presynaptic neurons release dopamine (DA) and noradrenaline (NA) into the synaptic cleft, where they act on NA receptors (NA-R) and DA receptors (DA-R) on the postsynaptic neuron membrane. In depressive states, the availability of these neurotransmitters is reduced, due both to insufficient release and to reuptake mediated by active DA (DAT) and NA (NET) transporters, which limits monoaminergic neurotransmission.

B, Bupropion (BP) inhibits DAT and NET transporters, blocking presynaptic reuptake of DA and NA, thereby increasing their concentration in the cleft and promoting neuronal transmission.